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International marketing trends and global advertisement: Analyzing the language barriers to efficient online marketing

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Abstract

International marketing trends and global advertisements are widely used by businesses to expand their reach to international audiences and boost sales. This paper examined international marketing trends with a focus on understanding the link between online marketing efforts and language barriers. The findings highlight the importance of linguistics simplicity, cultural adaptive content and accurate translation in enhancing the efficiency of online marketing. The findings reveal three main language-related barriers such as inaccurate translation, linguistic complexity and cultural insensitivity hindering online marketing efforts. The results stress the significance of culturally sensitive, clear and tailored communication in enhancing the efficiency of online marketing. The study provides useful insights for UAE companies to engage in effective marketing techniques to reach a global audience by addressing language barriers identified in the research.

Keywords: International Marketing; Online Marketing; Language Barriers; Multilingual Marketing; Global Advertisement

1. Introduction

Traditional marketing used to be mostly about advertising via billboards, television (TV), newspapers and posters, but these may not be as effective as they were a decade ago [1]. The new era of globalisation has transformed business operations and marketing techniques including the introduction of online marketing providing high connectivity and global access. Digital or online marketing has provided a platform for businesses to experiment and incorporate several strategies and approaches to achieve desired marketing results. This includes e-mail direct marketing, social media marketing, content automation, campaigns, e-commerce marketing, e-books, e-newspapers, and many more [2, 3]. The changing trends in marketing have led to a preference towards social media networks like Facebook, Twitter and YouTube as marketing communication mediums [4]. Online marketing has also addressed one of the most important limitations of traditional marketing such as accessing people who are outside the country or certain local. This is done by taking advantage of connectivity and access provided by the internet and digital platforms to audiences all over the world. This involves sending messages digitally to a wide range of consumers, the content is usually created and organized to reach different countries and automatically translates to its national language. For instance, the UAE is a multilingual country and has a diverse population of non-Emiratis including Indians, Pakistanis, Filipinos, and many others who come to earn bread for their families [5, 6]. However, Arabic and English are the two most prevalent languages, the latter as the lingua franca and the former as the official language [5, 7]. However, the Emirati locals in UAE are more of a minority when it comes to its diverse population. There are about 100 languages spoken in the UAE, and that does not include the variations of the Arabic language itself [7]. Objectionably, only 9 languages, other than English and Arabic, are stated in its official fact sheet for knowledge sharing [8]. Especially, when the government welcomes people

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with the slogan indicating that there are about 195 nationalities in Dubai alone [9]. Thus, UAE is a linguistically diverse country with a high rate of foreign population. This presents a barrier faced by service sector companies in UAE that use language to persuade or convince consumers to use their products/services. Likewise, companies in UAE targeting international audiences from other countries also face issues in their approach to using online marketing. It is necessary to understand the language barriers they face to develop strategies to address this issue and increase the international consumer base and loyalty for UAE companies.

About 30 years ago, language was not as important, it was shown that only a few authors thought that language was important whereas many of these did not deeply understand the complexities involved. However, things have changed as international scholars have started focusing on the complexity of language including its cultural-specific pragmatics and cross-cultural elements. Pragmatics is all about understanding different patterns in speech and patterns that comprehend how the speakers of different languages use certain phrases or words to make specific meanings. The use of simply translating the webpages in international marketing calls for a critical lens to be adopted, it is imperative to first understand the difficulties of translations and then to analyze the gap between what is being implied and what is understood by the targeted audiences of international marketing. The implied meaning might not be perceived as desired by international marketers creating misunderstanding for the audiences and leading to the inefficacy of online marketing. Drawing upon this idea, the present paper stresses the significance of understanding the language barriers that may impact online marketing content that is targeted towards international audiences. The first step to solving the issue of language barriers limiting the effectiveness of online international marketing is to understand the problem and the factors of language that act as barriers. With this objective in mind, the present paper is written to strengthen the process of international marketing and global advertising through the identification of language-related barriers to online marketing.

2. Literature Review

2.1. International Marketing Trends and Global Advertisement

Globalisation has transformed and opened doors for various opportunities for businesses to reach global audiences through global advertisement and connecting beyond borders. There has been a shift from traditional marketing approaches to international and modern marketing approaches. Investigating how firms can do more with fewer resources, Ahlberg and Einarsson [1] highlighted that traditional marketing in terms of TV ads and posters is no longer effective. Strategies like event marketing, product placement, marketing through public relations (PR) and brand management became popular. This soon changed as technological advancements and globalisation found their way to the advertising and marketing field in the form of digital marketing. Digital marketing can be understood as using technologies to facilitate marketing activities to enhance customer knowledge and meet their needs. Studies [2, 3] have used the terms digital marketing and online marketing interchangeably drawing upon the similarities and strengths to provide desirable benefits for the businesses competing in the international markets. Businesses can benefit from digital marketing by gaining maximum reach to consumers through search engine optimisation (SEO) and search engine marketing (SEM). Both provide an online form of marketing that purposely makes the content of a website or webpage highly relevant to search engines and keywords used by potential consumers. However, there is little research done on this issue to understand the interaction between multilingual marketing techniques and the use of SEO and SEM to effectively deliver the message to the targeted international audience [10]. What is further not clear in multilingual marketing is how exactly SEO and SEM work in different languages to capture the keywords.

2.2. Online Marketing and Multilingual Advertising

The literature on online marketing widely focuses on stressing the importance of online marketing by highlighting the limitations and challenges and traditional marketing techniques. As opposed to traditional marketing, online marketing is real-time and allows tracking and monitoring to observe whether a campaign is working [2]. The feedback evaluation results in implications for modifications for reaching the targeted audience in a better way. Regardless of the medium or type of online marketing, businesses need to engage in effective marketing strategies to gain maximum benefits from it. Paşcalău and Urziceanu [3] stated that while traditional marketing operates locally, online marketing operates globally to lessen the communication barriers. Agreeing with this, we acknowledge that online mediums and websites have made it possible to reach an audience residing in any area of the globe as opposed to TV and radio which only cover a certain geographical range. This might have reduced communication barriers leaving out loopholes in terms of addressing language barriers. One may argue that one of the ways to address language barriers in efficient online marketing is for everybody to learn the English language. However, such a solution is not feasible or even achievable shortly, especially with the statistics suggesting that only 1.5 billion people out of approximately 8 billion people in 2023 speak the English language as their first or second language [11, 12]. Moreover, recent research demonstrated

that the English language does not necessarily influence the product image or price but it has a significant influence on how the text is comprehended [13]. About 40% of the text in advertisements in the English language was not comprehended correctly as per survey responses and analysis filled by European countries even though the study included highly educated female consumers for whom the advert was created and intended [13]. This presents the case that not all advertisements of marketing content written in the English language are preferred or favourably comprehended by online consumers [14]. Thus, using the English language for all the marketing messages targeted to gain access to international consumers is not an effective, or sustainable, approach for UAE marketing companies.

Online marketing through websites tends to send identical versions of the webpages for every country using multilingual marketing techniques to translate pages into multiple languages based on the selected country [3]. Advertising and marketing are crucial for businesses as it is among the primary ways of increasing sales and enhancing overall financial performance. Marketing as a mediator between products/services and their potential buyers can influence economic indicators of the business. Kozlova [15] argued that the intercultural communication window views advertising as a platform facilitating interactions among a variety of cultures and sub-cultures. It is a type of systematic, non-personal and intended verbal and non-verbal communication to deliver messages to diverse audiences. With its increased complexity and multifaceted approach to advertising, the multilingual strategy is aimed at achieving persuasion, information sharing and gaining access to international consumers. Codeswitching and codemixing are often used by marketing analysts, codeswitching occurs when the native language is combined with expressions from the lingua franca or English. While codeswitching is involved with larger units, codemixing occurs when smaller units like certain terms or morphemes are inserted. These techniques allow marketing analysts to ensure emotionality, expressiveness and salience of the concepts used in the advert to deliver the message effectively. These bilingual adverts are also made with variations of the same language like different varieties of English to target specific ethnicity or region. This all facilitates the process of creating culturally sensitive and consumer-friendly marketing content to attract an international audience. Despite the significance of language as a powerful tool, the research on multilingual marketing in the UAE has gained inadequate research. To the best of the researcher's knowledge, no study extensively explored language barriers that may hinder the online marketing used by UAE companies to target global audiences that are inside and outside the country.

2.3. Theoretical Foundation

The current study draws upon the communication accommodation theory (CAT) that became prominent in the early 1970s originally as a sociopsychological model to examine different accents and shifts in multilingual interactions [16]. CAT underwent several modifications and refinements to appear as a multi-disciplinary framework for identity and relational processes in communication and interactions. Language is the central focus of the theory other symbols are also relevant and can be viewed from the lens of CAT. CAT suggests that people tend to naturally modify their language structure, speech patterns, vocabulary, accent and non-verbal cues, during a conversation, to either become similar (converge) or distinguish (diverge) from the other person. These accommodations are made because of several factors such as social acceptance, the context of the conversation and perceptions of dissimilarity or similarity.

The present study is interested in examining how language barriers shape international marketing efforts targeted towards wide audiences through online mediums. For this, CAT provides a strong framework and theoretical basis to stress the significance of language components and factors that can shape and influence the effectiveness of the intended marketing messages. CAT recognizes that accommodation and modification of language is a complex phenomenon that is influenced by several factors including psychological and social [16].

In the current study context, CAT provides a systematic approach to examine how language-related factors or components such as translation barriers may influence the efficiency of online marketing. In multicultural environments, marketing officials and companies are often faced with selling products to international audiences that are linguistically and culturally diverse. CAT becomes beneficial as it highlights the complexities of language accommodation, enlightening how language barriers may shape, either positively or negatively to influence the effective communication between businesses and their consumers via online mediums.

2.4. Language Barriers

Language barriers disrupt the intended message by the marketing companies, this influences the desired results of the marketing such as increasing the sales or attracting new customers. Thus, these language barriers have been explored in this section in terms of their influence on the effectiveness and efficiency of online marketing techniques.

2.4.1. Translation Barrier (TB)

Multilingual marketing is also simply done by translating the advertisement which is written and executed in the local language for instance Arabic in UAE to the international audiences in English. This translation technique may not be as effective as desired by the marketing companies and the number of people viewing the adverts may not reflect the efficiency of online marketing in terms of achieving more consumers instead of just viewers. Furthermore, even if the acting is good and the viewers understand the advert fully or partially, the translated captions in English may not fully capture the intended message targeted towards a global audience. Translation, in advertising and marketing, should never be simply about the conversion of words from Arabic to English. Even with this case, English is not stabilized as the locals continue to evolve the interaction between Arabic and English in UAE, with the patterns of a new variety of English such as *Gulf English* becoming prominent, the complexities have increased. It involves distinct grammatical features and combines lexical borrowing from the Arabic language making it a variation of English spoken in the Gulf region [5].

Thus, the companies aiming to extend their consumer base beyond the home country's borders should understand the complexities that shape how the viewers or readers would receive the adverts [17]. The misunderstanding and incorrect comprehension of advertisements in English are common in people who speak English as their second language due to different terminologies [18]. A great example of multilingual advertisement is observed in the advert created by Honda to market the CR-V hybrid sports utility vehicle (SUV) to Asian American consumers using languages English, Vietnamese, Korean and Mandarin [19]. The *'Through the Window'* campaign targets a population that is Asian Americans using multiple languages implying that language barriers exist [19]. Although the campaign is very interesting in the way it approaches to include cultural elements there may as well be challenges in terms of accurate translations and retaining meanings of idiomatic expressions to deliver the intended message. Nevertheless, the above example implies that UAE companies ought to understand the importance of translation barriers as they influence how a particular advert is received from its targeted consumers.

The translation barrier may leave consumers disappointed, and possibly influence a company's attempt to attract a global audience, build trust and boost sales [17]. The analysis of Amazon's case is important in this regard as it makes the argument for existing translation barriers, 43% of the participants from UAE suggested that information on the website is missing in their local language [20]. About 41% and 55% of the total online consumers were found to buy only from the websites and read descriptions of products, respectively, in their native language such as Arabic [20]. This stresses the significance of localization not just translation of the content in UAE to increase sales by catering to the consumers' language preferences and needs. Based on the above discussion the following hypothesis is developed to test translation barriers and their significant influence on online marketing in UAE companies that target global audiences.

2.4.2. Linguistic Complexity Barrier (LCB)

For instance, Kozlova [15] highlighted that the English language in the South African market is highly varied and given this multifaceted nature, the marketers intend to develop advertisements using different variations using codeswitching. The advert from a manufacturer of precast concrete walls company, ALFA, developed a marketing message such as *"Stop Nonsense, Precast Walls"*. The term *stop nonsense* resonates with Black English speakers' patterns and behaviour allowing the marketers to make the advert received as culturally relevant for the local market [15]. This stresses the importance of understanding linguistic complexity and cultural adaptation to make the advert effective for the targeted audience. Drawing upon this, the example produces implications for the present paper that such an advert might not be equally received by the diverse population in UAE.

The linguistic complexity is evident in UAE as well, this can be understood best using the study O'Neill [14] on the practices of language adopted by young Emirati women in Dubai. The study findings indicated a complex relationship between the choice of language impacted by language ideologies, emotional elements, and linguistic inclinations. This involves preferring to use the Arabic variation of the English language, or the Roman script, to communicate with friends and family that are Emiratis [14]. Even though nowadays smartphones have options to use the Arabic language with improved keyboard support overcoming the issues people face using social network applications like MSN messenger, Snapchat or Instagram; Emiratis are somewhat inclined to use Roman script [14]. Likewise, Hornikx, et al. [21] found that Dutch-speaking respondents preferred advertisement slogans in their native language as opposed to English language because of the complexity of the language. Linguistic complexity should be explored further and must be carefully examined by marketing companies in the UAE to ensure that efficient online marketing achieves what it aims through targeting the population internationally.

From the above, we argue that linguistic complexities have not been extensively explored in the context of international marketing and global advertisements conducted by UAE companies to gain access to consumers worldwide. The constant arrival and departure of people from diverse backgrounds in UAE also present an underlying challenge to identify what language, other than Arabic and English, can be considered useful. This highlights the complexities involved in multilingual marketing inside and outside of the UAE and presents a gap which needs to be filled by future research studies on the subject.

2.4.3. Cultural Adaptation barrier (CAB)

Several studies in the past have stressed the importance of focusing on cultural elements and cultural adaptation to increase the success of efficiency of international marketing. Roffman [22] examined the effectiveness of globalised international marketing against standardized international marketing. The authors analyzed the cases of multinational food corporations such as Burger King and McDonald's and found that they used a globalised approach which made them successful [22]. Specifically, marketing messages should be modified, to make them culturally relevant and adaptive, to attract customers based on the region or location. The study provided useful implications for businesses who failed to adapt to local cultures, the implications are useful and applicable for online marketing as well. Multilingualism is becoming normalized across different countries but online marketing messages targeted towards global audiences can be misunderstood due to the presence of diverse cultures and values [23]. Apart from language barriers, translation and linguistic complexity barriers, cultural adaptation barriers can also be challenging. Studies [22, 23] explained that cultural understanding allows individuals to respect different values and beliefs than their own and dismiss biases towards other cultures. Cultural norms are developed and followed as a rule that captures values and beliefs, these norms influence the behaviour of people who engage in online shopping [24]. Thus, online marketing messages must capture cultural meanings and values to effectively reach the intended audiences. Similarly, cultural elements should be considered to avoid insensitive marketing messages that can negatively impact the efficiency of online marketing efforts. For instance, consider the word 'luxury' which is often used in marketing content in Western cultures, *luxury* is associated with premium and high-quality products. However, the cultural meaning of *luxury* is not the same in Eastern languages, it is used for excessive or lavishness which is not necessarily considered positive in all scenarios. This translation barrier can impact how audiences may engage and perceive marketing content promoting *luxury* items. Thus, assessing the audiences in the UAE and tailoring the marketing messages accordingly is necessary to avoid negative impacts on online marketing efforts.

2.5. Hypotheses Development and Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework and Hypotheses

- H1a: Translation difficulties hinder international marketing efforts among online consumers.
 - H1b: Inaccurate translation of product information hinders international marketing efforts among online consumers.
 - H1c: Disjointed translation hinders international marketing efforts among online consumers.
 - H2a: Complex words hinder international marketing efforts among online consumers.
 - H2b: Difficult vocabulary hinders international marketing efforts among online consumers.
 - H2c: Clarity hinders international marketing efforts among online consumers.
 - H3a: Culturally mismatched content hinders international marketing efforts among online consumers.
 - H3b: Culturally sensitive content hinders international marketing efforts among online consumers.
 - H3c: Culturally irrelevant content hinders international marketing efforts among online consumers.
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3. Materials and Methods

An online survey questionnaire was designed and developed to learn more about the language barriers that can hinder the efficiency of online marketing strategies. The survey was filled by 400 which is a 100% response rate. The respondents were from different cultures and had diverse backgrounds. The multilingual and diverse population in UAE provided the benefit of reaching potential participants, all the respondents owned a mobile phone and used the internet. The sample population were accessed and included in the study using a convenience sampling technique to achieve a larger dataset by utilising the flexibility and access to the respondents [25]. To ensure that an acceptable response rate is achieved, reminders were sent to the respondents via email to fill out the survey as per their suitability and convenience.

The survey questionnaire comprised 13 items in total, for collecting demographic information 3 items were used and 10 related to consumers' perceptions about 3 categories of language barriers and its influence on online marketing efforts that result in consumer purchasing behaviour. The 3 categories of language barriers included in the study are translation barriers, linguistic complexity barriers, and cultural adaptation barriers. All items related to language barriers and online marketing were captured using a 5-point Likert Scale which ranged from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5) [26]. To ensure that language barriers do not hinder the effectiveness of delivering the intended message of this survey, the items were provided in English and as well as Arabic.

4. Results

4.1. Demographics

The collected data was analyzed using different statistical analysis techniques using Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) version 21. Initially, descriptive analysis was performed followed by regression analysis to assess the significance of the identified language factors to the efficiency of online marketing in UAE. The descriptive analysis showed that the data was biased towards a greater number of respondents being active internet users and having online shopping experiences. While 100% of respondents were internet users, 52.59% of these were males and 47.50 were females. The data was also found to be biased towards the middle-aged with more than 40% lying in the 30-39 age group, 20% within the 40-49 age group, 29% lying in the 20-29 age group and the remaining 11% in the 50 plus age group.

4.2. Hypothesis Testing

A multiple linear regression analysis was performed to understand the effect of language barriers on efficient online marketing. The beta coefficients show the direction of the effect and the importance of the variables. Table 1 shows that there exists a statistically significant difference in efficient online marketing based on the language barriers, the model summary is provided below. The R-value of the model is 0.284 which means that the model predicts about 28.4% of the variation that is contributed by the language barriers. This value indicates a correlation or existing relationship between the IV and DV. The R-squared value shows that overall variation in the DV due to all the IVs which is 8.1% in the current case. This indicates that the DV in the model is influenced by a wide range of factors that are not included in the model [27]. It means that the efficiency of online marketing is also influenced by factors other than language barriers for instance marketing techniques or overall market reach.

Table 1 Summary of the Model

Model	R	R-squared	Adjusted R-squared	Std. Error
1	0.284	0.081	0.060	0.81

Table 2 shows the ANOVA table and the associated F-statistic which indicates the model is highly significant with a p-value <0.001 and a rounded F value of 4. According to Kissell and Poserina [27], the value of $F > 2.5$ is acceptable. The residual sum of squares value is 775.75 which indicates the unexplained variation in the efficiency of online marketing.

Table 2 ANOVA

	Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	68.28	9	7.58	3.815	0.000
	Residual	775.75	390	1.989		
	Total	844.04	399			

To understand how the IVs significantly predict a change in the DV, it is necessary to assess beta coefficient values. Table 3 is included below which shows multiple regression analysis results. The t- t-statistics for the predictor's translation barriers such as TB2 (0.000) and linguistic complexity barriers (LCB) such as LCB2 (0.003) and LCB3 (0.002) show high statistical significance such as $p < 0.005$. Moreover, cultural adaptation barriers (CAB) such as CAB2 (0.02) are also statistically significant such as $p < 0.05$. As opposed to this, the t-statistics for the translation barriers TB1 and TB3 are not significant. Similarly, the linguistic complexity barrier LCB1 and cultural adaptation barriers CAB1 and CAB3 do not significantly predict change in the DV efficient online marketing. Thus, the analysis results indicate that there is supportive evidence to accept hypotheses H1a, H2b, H2c and H3b.

Table 3 Hypothesis Summary

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	4.622	0.870		5.312	0.000	2.911	6.333
	TB1	-0.046	0.056	-0.041	-0.817	0.414	-0.156	0.064
	TB2	-0.524	0.140	-0.209	-3.756	0.000	-0.798	-0.250
	TB3	0.122	0.142	0.048	0.863	0.388	-0.156	0.400
	LCB1	-0.025	0.062	-0.024	-0.409	0.683	-0.147	0.096
	LCB2	-0.329	0.109	-0.161	-3.019	0.003	-0.543	-0.115
	LCB3	0.168	0.055	0.175	3.047	0.002	.060	0.277
	CAB1	-0.030	0.056	-0.029	-0.539	0.590	-0.141	0.080
	CAB2	0.286	0.129	0.128	2.222	0.027	0.033	0.539
	CAB3	0.043	0.065	0.038	0.664	0.507	-0.085	0.172

5. Discussion

The research findings are important for practice and theoretical domains related to online marketing efficiency. The study provides useful insights regarding language barriers and how they may influence the efficiency of online marketing efforts. The results produce implications for practice for the UAE companies aiming to global audiences via

international marketing. The research study included several language barriers in terms of translation, linguistic complexity and cultural adaptation barriers. Through analysis, it is found that inaccurate translation, difficult vocabulary, lack of clarity and culturally insensitive content are important factors of language barriers that impact the efficiency of online marketing of UAE companies aiming to reach global audiences.

Among the factors, translation barriers such as inaccurate translation are found to be highly significant in influencing the efficiency of online marketing for UAE companies. The t-statistic value is significant (Sig =0.000) and the beta coefficient is -0.20 which shows a negative association between inaccurate translation and online marketing efficiency. The findings are consistent with previous studies [17, 18] which have also highlighted the importance of accurate translation including contextual and cultural information that helps in delivering the intended message. The translation process involves several factors instead of just words which contributes to the overall effectiveness of communication in marketing content [10]. Thus, inaccurate translation can significantly hinder the efficiency of online marketing of UAE companies and ought to be considered important by UAE companies.

The analysis also revealed that linguistic complexity barriers are also important language barriers that influence the efficiency of online marketing. Specifically, difficult or high vocabulary in addition to lack of clarity is found to have a significant influence on online marketing efficiency with significant p values of 0.003 and 0.002, respectively. The t-statistic of the high/difficult vocabulary reveals a beta coefficient value of -0.16 which shows a negative association with online market efficiency. This means that if the marketing content contains difficult or high vocabulary, it leads to a decrease in the efficiency of online marketing efforts for UAE companies. As opposed to this, a lack of clarity in the marketing content also influences the efficiency of online marketing with a beta coefficient value of 0.17. Overall, the complexity of the language used for marketing context influences the efficiency of online marketing. These findings are comparable with previous findings, which have stressed the importance of clear and effective communication in online marketing. For instance, Hornikx, et al. [21] found that respondents who spoke English as a second language preferred slogans in their native language because they found the language too complex.

The multiple regression results also reveal that culturally adapted content is likely to lead to the efficiency of only marketing. Specifically, culturally sensitive content positively impacts the efficiency of online marketing for UAE companies targeting international audiences. This stresses the importance of using marketing content that is culturally aware and signifies the existing cultural differences among the targeted audience. Previous studies [15, 22] have also found that cultural aspects play an important role in the effectiveness of multilingual marketing. Thus, cultural aspects are important for online consumers as it allows them to relate to the content and significantly influence the efficiency of online marketing.

6. Conclusion

The research explores and reveals language barriers that can influence the efficiency of online marketing targeted towards international audiences, especially in UAE companies engaged in international marketing. The findings are valuable as they stress the importance of using accurate translation, simple language and culturally sensitive content to enhance the efficiency of online marketing. Inaccurate translation hinders the effectiveness of marketing messages which can lead to inefficiency in terms of fewer new customers and sales. Accurate translation of product/service descriptions is more likely to attract new customers and engage the existing customers effectively to convey the intended marketing messages. These results correspond to previous findings and provide valuable insights for international marketers to double-check accurate translations in their marketing campaigns and advertisements via online mediums. In addition to this, linguistically complex language also leads to confusion and ambiguity hindering the smooth delivery of the intended message. The marketing messages developed using complex vocabulary and lack of clarity are statistically linked to negatively influencing the efficiency of online marketing. This stresses the importance of using clear language and simple linguistics to reduce the influence of linguistics complexity barrier on efficient online marketing. Additionally, it is recommended that transparent communication and straightforward language should be used to enhance the efficiency of online marketing.

The study also stresses the vital role of culturally aware of culturally adaptive marketing content in boosting the efficiency of online marketing. Culturally sensitive marketing messages are found to have a positive statistical significance with online marketing efficiency. It means that marketers should recognize cultural differences and use culturally adaptive language to improve access to international audiences. The findings of the present research are valuable as they provide insights for marketing companies to succeed in the complex landscape of multilingual marketing. By identifying and addressing the language barriers, businesses in the UAE and other Arab countries can enhance the efficiency of their online marketing techniques.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

There are no conflicts of interest

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

References

- [1] K. Ahlberg and P. Einarsson, "A Comparative Study of Traditional Marketing and Doing More with Less," Jonkoping International Business School, 2008.
- [2] M. Baala and D. Varma, "A Critical Review of Digital Marketing," *International Journal of Management, IT & Engineering*, vol. 8, no. 10, pp. 321-339, 2018.
- [3] V. S. Paşcalău and R. M. Urziceanu, "Traditional Marketing Versus Digital Marketing," *Agora International Journal Of Economical Sciences*, vol. 14, p. 5, 2020.
- [4] T. Zaimovic and A. Sutrovic, "Online vs Traditional; Marketing Challenge in the Telecom Market in Bosnia and Herzegovina," *Journal of Economics and Business*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 45-57, 2018.
- [5] P. Siemund, A. Al-Issa and J. Leimgruber, "Multilingualism and the role of English in the United Arab Emirates," *World Englishes*, pp. 1-14. Available at: DOI: 10.1111/weng.12507 [Accessed 7 Aug 2023], 2020.
- [6] R. Warner and I. A. Moonesar, "Diversity Management: The Case of the United Arab Emirates," *Diversity within Diversity Management*, vol. 21, pp. 41-64, 2019.
- [7] S. Hopkyns and M. v. D. Hoven, "Linguistic diversity and inclusion in Abu Dhabi's linguistic landscape during the COVID-19 period," *Multilingual*, vol. 41, no. 2, pp. 201-232, 2022.
- [8] UAE, "UAE Fact sheet," 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://u.ae/en/about-the-uae/fact-sheet>. [Accessed 2023].
- [9] I. Piller, "Dubai: Language in the ethnocratic, corporate and mobile city," in *MetroLinguistics: Urban Language Ecologies around the World*, D. Smakman and P. Heinrich, Eds., Routledge, 2017, pp. 1-22.
- [10] M. D. Mooij, "Translating Advertising," *The Translator*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 179-198, 2014.
- [11] SRD, "Population - Statistics & Facts," 2023a. [Online]. Available: <https://www.statista.com/topics/776/population/#topicOverview>. [Accessed 3 Aug 2023].
- [12] SRD, "The most spoken languages worldwide in 2023," 2023b. [Online]. Available: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/266808/the-most-spoken-languages-worldwide/>. [Accessed 3 Aug 2023].
- [13] M. Gerritsen, C. Nickerson, A. v. Hooft, F. Meurs, H. Korzilius and U. Nederstigt, "English in Product Advertisements in Non-English-Speaking Countries in Western Europe: Product Image and Comprehension of the Text," *Journal of Global Marketing*, vol. 23, no. 4, pp. 349-365, 2010.
- [14] G. T. O'Neill, "Multilingualism and occluded diversities within the superdiverse conditions of the United Arab Emirates: A study of the multiple language resources, practices and ideologies of young Emirati women," Macquarie University, 2017.
- [15] T. Kozlova, "Efficiency of Business and Intercultural Communication: Multilingual Advertising Discourse," *Advances in Economics, Business and Management Research*, vol. 129, pp. 272-278, 2020.
- [16] H. Giles, "Accent mobility: A model and some data.," *Anthropological Linguistics*, vol. 15, pp. 87-109, 1973.
- [17] K. L. Smith, "The Translation of Advertising Texts: A Study of English-Language Printed Advertisements Translations in Russian," University of Sheffield, 2002.
- [18] A. Konovalova and G. R. Yepes, "The Language of Marketing and Its Translation: Morphological and Semantic aspects of Terminology," *MonTI 8trans*, pp. 1-25, 2016.
- [19] A. Baar, "Honda targets Asian Americans with CR-V ads in multiple languages," 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.marketingdive.com/news/honda-asian-americans-cr-v-ad-mandarin-vietnamese-korean/637149/>. [Accessed 15 Sep 2023].

- [20] E. Angri, "How To Localize Amazon UAE Content To Boost Conversions? " 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://marginbusiness.com/amazon-uae-localization/>. [Accessed 7 Aug 2023].
- [21] J. F. Hornikx, V. Meurs and D. A. Boer, "English or a local language in advertising? The appreciation of easy and difficult English slogans in the Netherlands," *The Journal of Business Communication*, vol. 47, no. 2, pp. 169-188, 2010.
- [22] N. Roffman, "The Cultural Impact on International Marketing: Understanding How Different Cultures Influence Advertising Perception and How Different Cultures Influence Advertising Perception and How Different Cultures Influence Advertising Perception and Strategies," Bowling Green State University, 2023.
- [23] R. Al Karim, "The Cultural Impact on International Marketing Strategy, With a Special Emphasis of Bangladesh Perspective," *International Journal of Business and Technopreneurship*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 183-204, 2015.
- [24] G. Hemalatha, P. Anusuyadevi and S. Tamilsarasi, "The Cultural Impact On International Marketing Strategy, With A Special Emphasis of Retail Perspective," *SSRG International Journal of Economics and Management Studies*, vol. April, no. Special Issue, pp. 41-47, 2017.
- [25] J. Golzar, "Convenience Sampling," *International Journal of English Literature and Social Sciences*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 72-76, 2022.
- [26] A. Joshi, S. Kale, S. Chandel and D. K. Pal, "Likert Scale: Explored and Explained," *Current Journal of Applied Science and Technology*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 396-403, 2015.
- [27] R. Kissell and J. Poserina, "Chapter 2 - Regression Models," in *Optimal Sports Math, Statistics, and Fantasy*, Academic Press, 2017, pp. 39-67.